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‘Being Human is Being Who You Are’: The Being of Technology and the Becoming of Humans

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Abstract: Artificial Intelligence is occupying an inevitable place in our lives. There is steady progress in research too. Machine learning, AI domains, and algorithms are taught even in schools. Knowingly or unknowingly we encounter AI in our everyday life. And the world is slowly becoming dependent on AI. The recent pandemic has highlighted the importance of search engines. At this juncture, there are many relevant questions. What does it mean to be human in the age of Artificial Intelligence? What does it mean to be with others in the age of Artificial Intelligence? What does mean to be unique? Are we losing our identity with the use of search engines? This paper addresses the very essence of Being Human and the essence of Being who You Are in the age of Artificial Intelligence.

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“You may not realize it, but Artificial Intelligence is all around us” – Judy Woodruff, American broadcast journalist

Introduction

We are surrounded by AI. It will not be alarming news for some but for others, it will be a shock. We all are netizens in the present world. Day after day we are influenced by the search engines, different sites, Tubes, etc. Through these virtual worlds, the AI algorithms learn a person’s interest and accordingly they provide recommendations for the user. These recommendations of the AI algorithms can take us for a ride. The human being can turn out to be a machine. Therefore, it is important to understand and constantly clarify the meaning of being human in an AI world. So Carl Sagan, American astronomer, planetary scientist, and cosmologist, affirms: “Everyone is, in the cosmic perspective, precious. If a human disagrees with you, let him live. In a hundred billion galaxies, you will not find another” (Sagan 1980).

In this pale blue planet earth, dots, seconds, minutes, days, months, years and ages pass on. Who can claim that this is me, you are you and they are they? We, as who we are, can define what this is and several other intriguing questions. ‘Being human in the age of Artificial Intelligence’ turn out to be the key question.

This article gives an idea about how to be a human in the age of Artificial Intelligence, that is, ‘Being Human is Being As You Are’.

What does it mean by ‘Being who You are’ in the age of Artificial Intelligence?

Who You Are

Carl Sagan says, in a cosmic perspective you are ‘precious’; precious as human beings when compared with other beings and non-beings. I would certainly agree with him and say that we will not find such a complex being in hundred billion galaxies; a being with complex neuron networks, brain activities, mental activities, emotional variations, thought patterns, physical structure, kinaesthetic activities and skin texture etc. and a being which is precious because of its uniqueness.

In the modern world, technology can define who you are. Technology has taken giant leaps over the years. First, in the manner of hand-writing, we were unique. Then with the coming of the typewriter, we all became the same with the one writing style of the instrument (Sergeant, 2019: 108). However, in this netizen world, we are unique; unique in the form of codes and numbers. With the help of deep learning mechanisms used by Google, YouTube and other companies we are defined with the Googling (searching) patterns. Therefore, a search history can be used to define who you are. As we all know, each person has certain combinations of interests. Accordingly, the person searches his or her areas of interest. With those Googling patterns we can easily identify the characteristics of a person.

Can a search engine history define who you are? I would say, not yet. The Artificial Intelligence algorithm and deep mechanisms or techniques, which we employ today, are in its premature stage (Tamboli 2020). At this stage, it can define some patterns, but not more. With the development of technology, it can reach a stage where it can predict ‘you are 99.99 per cent the way you are’. However, as we see in the

Ludic fallacy¹, though we are clear of all the one hundred possible outcomes, yet a human can bring an outcome outside the possible sequels in hand.

The best example for the Ludic Fallacy would be the air crash investigation of US Flight 1549. According to the investigation officers with the help of computer flight simulations and outcomes, the flight would have crashed and the no one on board would have survived the crash. However, in reality with the given scenario, i.e., the bird strike-induced loss of engines, Captain Chesley Sully Sullenberger and the co-pilot Jeffrey Skiles took an outcome outside the box. They landed the plane in New York's Hudson River. All people on board survived the accident. (Tikkanen 2009) It shows that a simulation or an AI can define who you are to an extent within its limited boundaries in the present stage.

This unique outcome is a precious entity to us. Every person has his/her uniqueness. The very essence of us can be used to define who 'You Are'. It is who 'You Are' in the very depths of being a human.

Human? What does it mean to be a human? How can I be a human?

Being Human is Being With

Rationality, existentiality, social relationships, etc., can be used to define what it means to be human. At the depths of being a human, we can maintain that we are humans from the unique aspect of relationships (Bidshahri 2017). We

¹ Assuming flawless statistical models apply to situations where they actually don't. This can result in the over-confidence in probability theory or simply not knowing exactly where it applies as opposed to chaotic situations or situations with external influences too subtle or numerous to predict.

relate to the other not only in one way but from various perspectives. In the relationship, we might end up saying, “I want to be as the other”.

On a similar note, in the modern world, technology is allowing us to connect. The inter-personal relationships can be maintained with any person in the world, i.e., beyond the four walls of our rooms and meet a person at the other end of the world. Being connected to the other person allows us to explore and to gain more data. However, from a certain viewpoint, a person can say ‘I would like to be like him or her’, ‘I would like to have those things’, etc.

In other words, as Heidegger would say, he or she can get lost in the other world (They-Self) (Heidegger 2010: 268). He or she might lose his or her own self and dissolve in the world of the other.

Here, Being Human means not be someone else but as Jesus says, Being perfect as the Heavenly Father is. In other words, Being perfect means being loving, compassionate, understanding. to others while being with them. Therefore, in worldly terms, Being Human is loving, compassionate, understanding of others while being with others without losing our uniqueness.

How can we learn to be as perfect as the Heavenly Father is? Being human in this world we are on the road to becoming fully netizens. Being netizens, the world is exposed to us. We get enough and more examples of good people on the internet or the people around us. The present AI used by the big search engines does not have any biases. Therefore, it can show the examples fairly and we can learn about them from any part of the world.

Similarly, Being with oneself is also important. In other words, how are we comfortable in using our own human capabilities? Years ago, the use of paper or brain to do a math calculation

was highly appreciated. However, in these recent times, we are into the use of calculators and computers to do the same. Similarly, in the field of cars, we are inclined into the use of automatic cars than the manual shift ones by which we are losing the hand-leg-brain coordination which was important once. It is not about the calculative power or coordination we lose but it is about losing the things we are good at as humans. As the old saying says, “use it or lose it.” It is up to us to use what we have, that is, human actions or to lose it.

Nevertheless, Being Human netizens means not to be another person but learning to Be Human in this complex world. By being ‘As You Are’, you are ‘Being Human’ in Being with others and Being with one’s own human capabilities.

Being You

The basic structure of humane qualities allows us to act in our terms. In the sense of the modern world, I would say one should use mobile, hypertexts, social media, emoji and so on with the inalienable freedom to make the right choices.

In this day and age, the internet world or the AI world can give us a vast number of recommendations. As that it may, it does not mean that we should lose our own identity. In other words, one should be able to be ‘As You Are’, ‘Being Human’ and say ‘I am who I am’. ‘I am who I am’ is the revelation received by Moses as he witnesses the burning bush described in the book of Genesis in the Bible. Similarly, as the creators and consumers of AI in this modern world, we are gods or demigods. We should be able to say that I have my own stand, identity, freedom, will, choice in our Googling patterns and I want to go beyond the AI recommendations.

The internet world gives us various possibilities to think and express, free from constraints and cultures which promote restrictions (Anderson and Rainie 2018). Therefore, in this modern world, there is a tendency for the user to explore other possibilities to escape into the safe zone of a private and friendly virtual reality.

AI digital world provides a user-friendly virtual world (Punjabi n.d.). It provides opportunities according to one's own taste. The best example in the current times is the YouTube site. Anyone can create a channel and post his or her own videos. Similarly, when you have seen a video it automatically provides you related videos or recommendations. Here, you have to be yourself. In other words, you have to 'Be You' and you should have the will to go against the flow of the AI recommendations. Otherwise, these AI or AI algorithm recommendations in YouTube can rob our time for hours and hours. Therefore, 'Being You' means to be 'As You Are' and 'Being Human' means to be loving, compassionate, understanding and so on.

At the present times, the AI world as such does not discriminate between rich or poor or based on caste or religion. It does not show the rule of 80/20, the law of the vital few. It recognizes you as a human being. Therefore, even the poor can become a netizen in his or her own terms. He or she can voice their views to anyone in any part of the world.

In simple terms, an AI, if codified in a neutral sense, can give us various possibilities. Nonetheless, it is our choice to be 'As You Are' without losing the essence of 'Being Human' in the age of Artificial Intelligence.

Conclusion

As we move forward with the Artificial Intelligence the question remains is who will be controlling the AI world. History has proven the rule of 80/20 in a social scenario

without AI. As AI progresses in a research setup we do not feel the law of the vital few. Nonetheless, as the AI world advances, the few 20 can rule the other 80; which has already started in different forms. The giant corporations with the help of the virtual world compete to be a monopoly in certain fields. As the expert says, “Tools and systems are not always hurtful, people using them are” (Tamboli 2020). Once we have and learn a technology we can use it and it works for you. Nonetheless, ‘who you’ are depends on how you use the technology.

Therefore, we have to be conscious about the happenings in the virtual world to free ourselves from being deceived. As consumers of AI algorithms, we should have a certain determination not to be influenced by it but to be sapient and discerning in the use of the virtual world. This is a herculean task as we are surrounded by Artificial Intelligence and gradually deceived by it in small terms. Nevertheless, to be a ‘human’ and to be ‘who you are’ we should promote a culture that stands for the dignity of human Beingness.

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